
Effective Classroom Management

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SUMMARY

Existing Knowledge:

1. Classroom management is critical for creating conducive learning environments and achieving educational goals.
2. Teachers must master competencies like lesson planning, fostering discipline, and using engaging teaching methods.
3. Effective management integrates physical design, positive atmospheres, and strong teacher-student relationships.

New Insights:

1. Teachers' management skills were rated "good", highlighting strengths in communication, discipline, and physical environment design.
2. Areas needing improvement include using diverse media and methods to maintain student interest.
3. Democratic classroom management styles, combining rules with student collaboration, foster better engagement.

Putting Research into Practice:

1. Train teachers to implement varied instructional methods, incorporating technology and interactive activities.
2. Encourage classroom designs emphasizing visibility, flexibility, and comfort for an optimal learning experience.
3. Promote professional development to refine teachers' skills in maintaining discipline and positive classroom dynamics.

Keywords: classroom management, teacher skills, discipline, physical environment, student engagement, instructional methods

Reference:

Zainuddin, & Hardiansyah, F. (2023). Teacher classroom management skills and its implementation in primary school learning. *Mimbar Sekolah Dasar*, 10(1), 92-105. <https://doi.org/10.53400/mimbar-sd.v10i1.48865>

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